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INCREASED CITATIONS THROUGH OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING OR INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION: A STUDY OF ENGINEERING PUBLICATIONS

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INTRODUCTION

The reach and impact of scientific literature are always judged by the number of citations it gets. Although internet publishing has provided an opportunity to retrieve usage statistics, the impact of research publication is still arbitrated by citations only (McGillivray & Astell, 2019). With ease in internet publishing, the open access publication movement also gained momentum in the first decade of the 21st century (Davis & Walters, 2011). At the same time internet also made communications between the different geographies easy, which helped researchers located in different geographies and time zones to collaborate and communicate efficiently (Silvia & Iryna, 2012). Open access publishing and international collaborations are important reasons for increased research and research publications in scientific and academic communities. These factors also help to promote the research and its 'citability'.

Citability is the "ability of a publication to be citable". Various factors determine a publication about its 'citability', and these factors may differ from subject to subject and geography to geography. Citation is a scientific impact of a research publication and is used as an indicator to evaluate its scientific value (Aksnes et al., 2019). The current study focuses on the two factors that play a vital role in determining the citability of research publications: open access publishing and international collaborations in the engineering domain.

SIGNIFICANCE & LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The current study may clarify the impact of open-access publications and international collaboration in evaluating the research publication by Indian authors in the Engineering subject domain. The Study has a potential significance to the researchers in the field of Engineering and policymakers, administrators, and research funding agencies in designing their research priorities and publishing policies. It is also essential to study where Indian research stands compared with the global trends in various subject categories. Hence, this study is limited to evaluating the research impact of open access publishing and international collaboration in the Indian research publications in the Engineering subject domain published between 2011 and 2020 and indexed in the Web of Science database.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the current Study is to evaluate the impact of open access publishing and international collaboration on research publications by Indian authors in the engineering domain subject between 2011-20. The other objectives are:

1. To study the global publications and open-access trends in the Engineering subject;
2. To identify the open access publication trends among the Indian authors;
3. To identify the publications trends with international collaboration;
4. To determine the citability impact of open-access publishing and international collaboration on research publications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The bibliographic records for the Study were extracted from the Web of Science database published between 2011 and 2020. Of the 23,36,549 indexed bibliographic records in Engineering subject, 1,14,736 bibliographic records with at least one author with Indian affiliation are extracted. Further, publication records of open-access publications and internationally collaborated bibliographic records are extracted in Excel format in August 2022. Extracted data were further analyzed using MSExcel and mathematical and statistical formulae.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Year-wise distribution of publications

According to the Web of Science core collection database, the world has published 23,36,549 research papers in the 'Engineering' subject domain between 2011-2022. Nearly 26.02% of these publications are published as 'Open Access'. At the same time, 2,11,65,214 research papers were published between 2011-2020; among them, 76,83,001 (36.30%) were published as open access. Thus, the researchers in the Engineering domain lag behind the restin publishing their research as Open Access.

At the beginning study period, the open access publication trend in 2011 was recorded 14.34%, and the yearly percentage has continuously increased without any fall to 37.66% in the year 2020. Which is more than of global open access percentage for that decade. The year-wise global open access publication trend has shown linear growth, which indicates increasing awareness and interest in open access publishing among researchers in Engineering.

Among the 208 countries that contributed at least a single research paper in the Engineering subject domain, India is the third highest contributing country with 4.91% of global publications after Peoples R China (5,12,264, 21.92%), the USA (3,11,776, 13.34%). India has published 1,14,736 research publications in the Engineering subject domain between 2011-2020. In 2011, India's contribution to the global engineering domain was 3.66%, and the percentage gradually increased to 5.96% in 2020. So, during the period of the study, Indian contribution to the global publications in the Engineering domain has seen linear growth.

Table 1 Year-wise distribution of global publications Vs Open Access & Indian Publications

Year	TP-GL	TP-GL-OA	% of TP-GL	TP-IN	% of TP-GL
2011	168828	24213	14.34	6180	3.66
2012	179611	27985	15.58	6392	3.56
2013	190987	33941	17.77	7566	3.96
2014	198817	37966	19.1	8225	4.14
2015	212839	46742	21.96	9555	4.49
2016	226889	56777	25.02	11308	4.98
2017	245008	65959	26.92	13017	5.31
2018	267745	82070	30.65	14867	5.55
2019	308000	105000	34.09	17481	5.68
2020	337825	127222	37.66	20145	5.96
Total	2336549	607875	26.02	114736	4.91

TP-GL= Total Global Publications; TP-GL-OA= Total Global Open Access Publications; TP-IN= Total Indian Publications

Year-wise distribution of Indian publications

Table 2 depicts year-wise publication and citation trends among the research papers published in engineering between 2011-2022. Overall, during the Study, a total of 1,14,736 research publications were published in the Engineering domain, where at least one author is from India. To date, these 1,14,736 publications have received 18,79,697 citations at the rate of 16.38 citations per paper.

As year-wise publications have achieved linear growth, the lowest number of publications are recorded in 2011 (6180) and the highest number of publications in 2022 (20145). Whereas citations are concerned, the highest number of citations were received in the year 2018 (224133), followed by 2017 (224006) and 2016 (220050) and the lowest number of citations was recorded for the year 2015 (119440), followed by 2020 (163766) and 2012 (167698).

Across the study period, citations per paper (CPP) are recorded at 16.38. However, the highest number of CPP is recorded in the year 2011 (28.59), followed by 2012(26.24) and 2013(25.04); the lowest CPP is recorded for the year 2020(8.13), followed by 2019(11.57) and 2015(12.5). The h-index is also an important parameter which helps evaluate the cumulative impact of scholarly publications over time. According to the year-wise h-index, publications in the year 2011 received the highest 141 h-index, followed by 2012(134) and 2013(133), and the year 2020 recorded the lowest 78 h-index, followed by 2019(95) and 2018(106).

Table 2 Year-wise distribution of Indian publications.

Year	TP-IN	TC-IN	CPP-IN	h-index
2011	6180	176661	28.59	141
2012	6392	167698	26.24	134
2013	7566	189476	25.04	133
2014	8225	192226	23.37	132
2015	9555	119440	12.5	121
2016	11308	220050	19.46	121
2017	13017	224006	17.21	111
2018	14867	224133	15.08	106
2019	17481	202241	11.57	95
2020	20145	163766	8.13	78
Total	114736	1879697	16.38	

TP-IN=Total Indian Publications; TC-IN=Total Citations for Indian Publications; CPP-IN=Citations per Paper for Indian Publications

Year-wise distribution of Indian open access publications

Indian contribution to open access publications in Engineering domains is 13,556, which is 11.81% of overall Indian publications in the Engineering domain. At the beginning of the study period, the percentage of open access publications among the Indian authors was 6.76% (2011), which increased to 15.85% by the end of the study period in 2020.

The highest number of open access publications by Indian authors in the engineering domain is recorded in the year 2020 (3193), followed by 2019(2430) and 2018(2095). The lowest is recorded for the year 2011 (418), followed by 2012(472) and 2013(621). Since 2011, the number of Indian open access publications are recorded linear growth on par with overall Indian publications in the Engineering domain. However, citations received for these Indian open access publications are concerned with the trend in contrast to the citations received by overall Indian publications in the Engineering domain as more recent publications have

received a good number of citations rather than older publications. A total of 220956 citations are received by the 13556, which is 11.75% of overall citations received by Indian publications in Engineering.

The Study calculated 16.30 citations per paper for the Indian open access publications during the study period, nearly equivalent to the CPP calculated for overall Indian publications in the Engineering domain. The highest CPP is recorded for the year 2011(26.54), followed by 2013(25.87) and 2012(25.05) and the lowest CPP was recorded for the year 2020(10.06), followed by 2019(13.19) and 2018(16.15). However, the h-index trend in Indian open access publications contrasts with the overall Indian publications in the Engineering domain. The highest h-index is recorded for the years 2018, and 2019 with 68, followed by 2017 (67) and the lowest h-index is recorded for the years 2012(51), followed by 2011(52) and 2014(54).

The percentage of open access articles in the Indian publications (11.81%) is deficient compared to the percentage of open access articles in global publications (26.02%) in the Engineering domain. Hence, Indian researchers need to speed up the pace to match global trends with more open-access publications.

Table 3 Year-wise distribution of Indian open access publications

Year	TP-IN-OA	% of TP-IN	TC-IN-OA	% of TC-IN	CPP-IN-OA	h-index
2011	418	6.76	11095	6.28	26.54	52
2012	472	7.38	11825	7.05	25.05	51
2013	621	8.21	16065	8.48	25.87	57
2014	674	8.19	14073	7.32	20.88	54
2015	840	8.79	15667	13.12	18.65	54
2016	1277	11.29	26156	11.89	20.48	67
2017	1536	11.8	28059	12.53	18.27	65
2018	2095	14.09	33833	15.10	16.15	68
2019	2430	13.9	32058	15.85	13.19	68
2020	3193	15.85	32125	19.62	10.06	60
Total	13556	11.81	220956	11.75	16.30	

TP-IN-OA=Total Indian Open Access Publications; TP-IN=Total Indian Publications; TC-IN-OA=Total Citations for Indian Open Access Publications; TC-IN=Total Citations for Indian Publications; CPP-IN-OA=Citations per Paper for Indian Open Access Publications

Year-wise distribution of Indian publications with International Collaborations

Table 4 of the research study depicts the other aspect of the Study, i.e., trends in the publications with international collaboration among the Indian publications in the Engineering subject domain. During the study period, 25,067 publications have international collaboration in the Engineering subject domain, which is 21.85% of overall Indian publications in the subject area. Identical to the overall Indian publications, International collaborated Indian publications in the Engineering domain have recorded a linear growth in the number of publications in the study period. In 2011, the number of publications with international collaboration was 1269, which increased gradually, and the number of publications recorded in 2020 was 5186.

The table also shows that these 25,067 international collaborated research publications have received 5,68,985 citations at the rate of 22.70 per paper. The highest number of citations are received in 2019(69028), followed by 2018(66584) and 2020(64810), and the lowest citations are received in 2012(43274), followed by 2011(45672) and 2014(50350). According to the percentage of the yearly citations received, the highest percentage is recorded in 2015(43.89%), followed by 2020(39.57%) and 2019(34.13). However, across the study period, the percentage of citations received is higher than the number of publications.

During the study period, publications with international collaborations have achieved 22.70, higher than the 16.38 CPP achieved for overall Indian publications in the Engineering domain. The highest CPP is recorded in the year 2011(35.99), followed by 2012(32.83) and 2013(31.84) and the lowest CPP is recorded in 2020(12.5), followed by 2019(17.35) and 2018(20.87). According to the h-index, the highest 96 h-index was recorded in 2016, followed by 2011(95) and 2014(94).

Table 4: Year-wise distribution of Indian publications with International Collaborations

Year	TP-IN-IC	%of TP-IN	TC-IN-IC	%of TP-IN	CPP-IN-IC	h-index
2011	1269	20.53	45672	25.85	35.99	95
2012	1318	20.62	43274	25.80	32.83	91
2013	1605	21.21	51100	26.97	31.84	91
2014	1619	19.68	50350	26.19	31.1	94
2015	1943	20.33	52418	43.89	26.98	91
2016	2325	20.56	61883	28.12	26.62	96
2017	2634	20.24	63866	28.51	24.25	90
2018	3190	21.46	66584	29.71	20.87	88
2019	3978	22.76	69028	34.13	17.35	88
2020	5186	25.74	64810	39.57	12.5	73
Total	25067	21.85	568985	30.27	22.70	

TP-IN-IC=Total Indian Publications with International Collaboration; TP-IN=Total Indian Publications; TC-IN-IC=Total Citations for Indian Publications with International Collaboration; TC-IN=Total Citations for Indian Publications; CPP-IN-IC=Citations per Paper for Indian Publications with International Collaboration

Year-wise distribution of Indian open access publications with international collaboration

Table 5 presents the analysis of the year-wise distribution of open access Indian publications with international collaboration; out of 13,556 open access Indian publications, 5,685 (41.94%) publications has at least an international author in collaboration. The number of internationally collaborated open access Indian publications is increasing year by year; in 2011 number of papers was 156, and by the end of the year, in the study period number reached 1658 in 2020. According to the share of internationally collaborated Indian open access publications, the highest percentage was in 2020 (51.93%), followed by 2019(44.49%) and 2016(38.84%), and the lowest was recorded in 2014(32.94%). These 5,685 research publications received 1,24,800 citations during the study period at 21.95 citations per paper. Although the percentage of open access Indian publications with international collaboration is 41.94, the percentage of citations received is 56.84.

Citations per paper (CPP) for the whole period is 21.95 for open access Indian publications with international collaboration is higher than the 16.30 CPP of open access Indian publications in the Engineering domain but at the same time is lower than the 22.70 CPP of Internationally collaborated Indian publications in Engineering domain. During the study period, the highest CPP is recorded in the year 2013(38.5), followed by 2012(37.98) and 2011(32.33) and the lowest is recorded in 2020(13.12), followed by 2019(18.72) and 2018(21.78). According to the h-index, the highest h-index is recorded in 2019(62), followed by 2016(60) and the lowest h-index in 2011(37), followed by 2012(39).

Table 5 Year-wise distribution of Indian open access publications with international collaboration.

Year	TP-IN-OA-IC	% TP-IN-OA	TC-IN-OA-IC	% TC-IN-OA	CPP-IN-OA-IC	h-index
2011	156	37.32	5044	45.46	32.33	37
2012	166	35.17	6305	53.32	37.98	39
2013	231	37.2	8894	55.36	38.5	43
2014	222	32.94	7102	50.47	31.99	41
2015	325	38.69	8154	52.05	25.09	48
2016	496	38.84	15119	57.80	30.48	60
2017	586	38.15	15555	55.44	26.54	57
2018	764	36.47	16641	49.19	21.78	57
2019	1081	44.49	20235	63.12	18.72	62
2020	1658	51.93	21751	67.71	13.12	56
Total	5685	41.94	124800	56.48	21.95	

TP-IN-OA-IC=Total Indian OA Publications with International Collaboration; TP-IN-OA=Total Indian OA Publications; TC-IN-OA-IC=Total Citations for Indian OA Publications with International Collaboration; CPP-IN-OA-IC=Citations per Paper for Indian OA Publications with International Collaboration

Trends in Citations per Paper with different parameters

The citations per paper (CPP) is a helpful parameter calculated by dividing the total number of citations by the total number of papers to evaluate the average impact of scholarly publications under Study. Table 6 depicts the citations per paper calculated for various categories discussed in previous tables for comparison based on the bibliographic records of Engineering domain Indian publications.

The publications with open access can potentially get more audience than those with closed or subscribed access. However, when compared, publications with international collaboration have received a higher average CPP (26.03) than the open access publications (19.51) without any international collaboration. At the same time, open access publications with international collaborations have the upper hand due to the collaborative open access advantage among all the other parameters and have received the highest average of 27.65 CPP.

Table 6 Trends in Citations per Paper with different parameters.

Year	CPP-IN	CPP-IN-OA	CPP-IN-IC	CPP-IN-OA-IC
2011	28.59	26.54	35.99	32.33
2012	26.24	25.05	32.83	37.98
2013	25.04	25.87	31.84	38.5
2014	23.37	20.88	31.1	31.99
2015	12.5	18.65	26.98	25.09
2016	19.46	20.48	26.62	30.48
2017	17.21	18.27	24.25	26.54
2018	15.08	16.15	20.87	21.78
2019	11.57	13.19	17.35	18.72
2020	8.13	10.06	12.5	13.12
Average	18.72	19.51	26.03	27.65

CPP-IN=Citations per Paper for Indian Publications; CPP-IN-OA=Citations per Paper for Indian Open Access Publications; CPP-IN-IC=Citations per Paper for Indian Publications with International Collaboration; CPP-IN-OA-IC=Citations per Paper for Indian OA Publications with International Collaboration.

In 2011, the highest CPP was recorded for Indian research papers with international citations; for the remaining years, open access to Indian publications with international citations. Thus, the result shows that the publications with international collaborations are likely to get higher citations rather than just an open access publication, and open access publications with international collaboration were significantly more likely to get more citations.

CONCLUSION

In the research publications, various factors determine its 'citability', which may differ from subject to subject and geography to geography. The current study attempts to verify the measurable scientific impact through citations on two critical factors, i.e., Open Access publishing and International Collaboration among the Indian publications in the Engineering subject domain. To verify which factor plays a vital role in increasing the 'citability' chances of research literature, the current study analyzed research publications with at least one Indian author in the Engineering Subject domain published between 2011-20 and indexed in the Web of Science database. The main focal point is the number of citations the publications under the study received.

The key finding of this study is that open access can provide an opportunity to reach a wider audience through easy and free access. Still, the international collaboration has likely brought more citations to the research publications in the Engineering subject domain. Hence, an open-access publication with international collaboration increases the research's impact and citability. Thus, the Indian researchers need more awareness about the benefits of publishing as open-access and policymakers, administrators and research funding agencies should support the researchers to publish their research as open-access through an open-access policy.

REFERENCES

1. Aksnes, D. W., Langfeldt, L., & Wouters, P. (2019). Citations, Citation Indicators, and Research Quality: An Overview of Basic Concepts and Theories. *SAGE Open*, 9(1), 215824401982957. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019829575>
2. Breugelmans, J. G., Roberge, G., Tippett, C., Durning, M., Struck, D. B., & Makanga, M. M. (2018). Scientific impact increases when researchers publish in open access and international collaboration: A bibliometric analysis on poverty-related disease papers. *PLOS ONE*, 13(9), e0203156. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0203156>
3. Bond, M., Marín, V. I., & Bedenlier, S. (2021). International Collaboration in the Field of Educational Research: A Delphi Study. *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research*, 10(2), 190–213. <https://doi.org/10.7821/naer.2021.7.614>
4. Harnad, S., & Brody, T. (2004). Comparing the Impact of Open Access (OA) vs. Non-OA Articles in the Same Journals. *D-Lib Magazine*, 10(6). <https://doi.org/10.1045/june2004-harnad>
5. Holmberg, K. (2019). *Do articles in open access journals have more frequent altmetric activity than articles in subscription-based journals? An investigation of the research output of Finnish universities*. SpringerLink. Retrieved September 10, 2022, from https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11192-019-03301-x?error=cookies_not_supported&code=e50092aa-0406-499a-89d5-ad32352d443e
6. Khor, K. A., & Yu, L. G. (2016). Influence of international co-authorship on the research citation impact of young universities. *Scientometrics*, 107(3), 1095–1110. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-1905-6>
7. Kousha, K., & Abdoli, M. (2010). The citation impact of Open Access agricultural research. *Online Information Review*, 34(5), 772–785. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14684521011084618>

8. Kwiek, M. (2020). What large-scale publication and citation data tell us about international research collaboration in Europe: changing national patterns in global contexts. *Studies in Higher Education*, 46(12), 2629–2649. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2020.1749254>
9. McGillivray, B., & Astell, M. (2019). The relationship between usage and citations in an open access mega-journal. *Scientometrics*, 121(2), 817–838. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03228-3>
10. Satish, N. G. (2021). International collaboration and high citation impact – A case analysis of immunology. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 68(4), 366–375.
11. Shettar, I. M., & Hadagali, G. S. (2021). Impact of Open Access Publication in Veterinary Sciences in India: A Scientometric Study. In K. N. Kandapal et al. (Ed.), *Libraries: From Clay Tablet to Fablet* (pp. 144–157). Agri-Biovet Press.
12. Silvia, R. D., & Iryna, B. (2012). The Influence of Online Communication and Web-Based Collaboration Environments on Group Collaboration and Performance. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, 935–943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.05.227>
13. Van Raan, A. F. J. (1998). The influence of international collaboration on the impact of research results: Some simple mathematical considerations concerning the role of self-citations. *Scientometrics*, 42(3), 423–428.
14. Velez-Estevez, A., García-Sánchez, P., Moral-Munoz, J. A., & Cobo, M. J. (2022). Why do papers from international collaborations get more citations? A bibliometric analysis of Library and Information Science papers. *Scientometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04486-4>
15. Wang, X., Liu, C., Mao, W., & Fang, Z. (2015). The open access advantage considering citation, article usage and social media attention. *Scientometrics*, 103(2), 555–564. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1547-0>